

Supporting Information for

Type-II CdSe/ZnO Core-Shell Nanorods: Nanoheterostructures with a Tunable dual Emission in Visible and Near-Infrared Spectral Ranges

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1. Calculations of Zn precursors requirements for ZnO shell.

Tables TS1-TS3 provide a summary of the calculations of the Zn(acac)₂ precursor needed for the preparation of the ZnO with a desired shell thickness. In the calculations, following parameters were used: ZnO lattice constant = 0.325 nm; ZnO density = 5.61 g/cm³; ZnO molecular weight = 81.39 g/mol; conc. of Zn(acac)₂ = 0.1 M.

Table TS1. Calculation of the Zn precursors requirements for ZnO shell for CdSe NRs with $\langle d \rangle = 3.2$ nm. Starting amount of CdSe NRs was 23.2 nmol.

Initial assumption: NR Diameter = 3.2 nm and Length = 10.7 nm			
nML	NR volume (nm ³)	ZnO shell volume (nm ³)	Precursor volume (mL)
0 ML	86.05	-	-
1 ML	132.13	46.08	0.44
3 ML	263.51	177.45	1.71
5 ML	455.81	369.76	3.55
7 ML	719.39	633.33	6.09

Table TS2. Calculation of the Zn precursors requirements for ZnO shell for CdSe NRs with $\langle d \rangle = 4.1$ nm. Starting amount of CdSe NRs was 3.1 nmol.

Initial assumption: NR Diameter = 4.1 nm and Length = 45.3 nm			
nML	NR volume (nm ³)	ZnO shell volume (nm ³)	Precursor volume (mL)
0 ML	598	-	-
1 ML	814.26	216.18	0.28
3 ML	1358.32	760.25	0.98
5 ML	2059.94	1461.86	1.88
7 ML	2929.46	2331.38	3.01

Table TS3. Calculation of the Zn precursors requirements for ZnO shell for CdSe NRs with $\langle d \rangle = 4.7$ nm. Starting amount of CdSe NRs was 3.1 nmol.

Initial assumption: NR Diameter = 4.7 nm and Length = 28.9 nm			
nML	NR volume (nm ³)	ZnO shell volume (nm ³)	Precursor volume (mL)
0 ML	501.40	-	-
3 ML	1071.49	570.09	1.43

2. NRs structural characteristics

Table TS4. Determination of the experimentally measured number of ZnO shell monolayers deposited on CdSe NRs. ML_{cal} and ML_{exp} are the numbers of theoretically and experimentally calculated ZnO monolayers deposited onto the CdSe NRs, respectively. $\langle d \rangle$ is the average diameter and $\langle l \rangle$ is the average length of the NRs. $AR = \langle l \rangle / \langle d \rangle$. V_{cal} and V_{exp} are the theoretically calculated and experimentally determined volumes of the NRs, respectively.

NRs	ML_{cal}	V_{cal} (nm^3)	$\langle d \rangle$ (nm)	$\langle l \rangle$ (nm)	AR	V_{exp} (nm^3)	ML_{exp}
1	0	501.40	4.7 ± 1.3	28.9 ± 7.7	6 ± 2	501.40	0
	3	1071.49	5.2 ± 0.8	35.2 ± 5.3	7 ± 1	747.55	1.5
2	0	598.08	4.1 ± 0.9	45.3 ± 8.2	11 ± 3	598.08	0
	3	1358.32	5.8 ± 1.2	51.5 ± 8.2	9 ± 2	1360.67	3
3	0	86.05	3.2 ± 0.2	10.7 ± 0.5	3.3 ± 0.3	86.05	0
	3	263.51	5.0 ± 0.2	12.65 ± 1.4	2.5 ± 0.3	243.47	2.74

3. HR BF and HAADF STEM analyses

Figure S1. (a,b) HAADF STEM images of (a) CdSe NRs ($\langle d \rangle = 3.2$ nm) and (b) CdSe-ZnO NRs (3 ML ZnO). The average diameter and length histogram of the core NRs are presented in (c-d) and the CdSe-ZnO NRs are shown in (e-f). The average length and diameter of the NRs increases as a result of the ZnO shell growth.

Figure S2. HAADF STEM images of CdSe NRs ($\langle d \rangle = 4.7$ nm) before and after 3 ML ZnO shell. (a) Core CdSe NRs, (b,c) diameter and length distribution histogram. (d) TEM image for core-shell CdSe-ZnO NRs. The average diameter and length of the core-shell NRs are shown in (e-f). The average length and diameter of the NRs increases after ZnO shell growth.

Figure S5. (a) BF STEM image of $\langle d \rangle = 4.1$ nm CdSe core with 3 ML of ZnO. (b) Fourier transform electron diffraction image showing the different planes. Red marked line indicates the CdSe and blue marked lines indicates the ZnO.

Figure S6. Representative HAADF STEM images of the $\langle d \rangle = 3.2$ nm CdSe core NRs (a) and CdSe/ZnO NRs after reaction with $\text{Zn}(\text{acac})_2$ corresponding to 1 ML (b), 5 ML (c) and 7 ML (d) ZnO shell. The histograms in Fig. 5 of the main text were generated via the analysis of multiple images for each of the samples.

4. EDS analysis

Figure S7. EDS spectrum of CdSe (d ~4.1 nm)-ZnO (3 ML) core-shell NRs.

Table TS5. Results of EDS analysis on CdSe (4.1 nm)-ZnO 3 ML core-shell heterostructure NRs.

Element	Mass%	At%
Cd	41.74	21.40
Se	40.90	29.85
Zn	3.18	2.80

5. Photoluminescence properties of NRs

Table TS6. The PL quantum yield of core CdSe NRs and 3 ML ZnO shell deposited on three different size CdSe NRs ($\langle d \rangle = 3.2$ nm, 4.1 nm and 4.7 nm). $\langle d \rangle$ is the average diameter of the NRs, ML_{cal} is the calculated number of ZnO monolayers, PL_{Core} is the peak position of the PL attributed to the radiative carrier recombination within the CdSe core on the wavelength/energy scale, PL_{T-II} is the peak position of the type-II PL on the wavelength/energy scale, PLQY is the total quantum yield. $PLQY_{Core}$ and $PLQY_{T-II}$ are the relative contributions of the “core” and type-II PL to the total PLQY.

NRs	ML_{cal}	PL_{Core} (nm/eV)	PL_{T-II} (nm/eV)	PLQY (%)	$PLQY_{Core}$ (%)	$PLQY_{T-II}$ (%)
$\langle d \rangle = 4.7$	0	613/2.02	-	0.17	100	-
	3	629/1.97	860/1.44	18.9	2.7	97.3
$\langle d \rangle = 4.1$	0	617/2.01	-	0.17	100	-
	3	632/1.96	870/1.43	6.1	7.2	92.8
$\langle d \rangle = 3.2$	0	552/2.25	-	1.8	100	-
	3	591/2.10	800/1.55	10.6	49.6	50.4

Table TS7. Lifetime of the three different sizes of the CdSe NRs and the corresponding CdSe/ZnO NR heterostructures with 3 ML of ZnO. All the lifetime data were fitted with a tri-exponential function. n-ML represents the number of calculated monolayers. A_1 , A_2 , and A_3 are the pre-exponential factors of the tri-exponential decay function. τ_1 , τ_2 , and τ_3 are the lifetime components. $\langle \tau_{avg} \rangle$ is the average lifetime calculated using a formula $\langle \tau_{avg} \rangle = \frac{\sum A_i \tau_i^2}{\sum A_i \tau_i}$.

$\langle d \rangle$ (nm)	n-ML	PL	A_1	A_2	A_3	τ_1 (ns)	τ_2 (ns)	τ_3 (ns)	$\langle \tau_{avg} \rangle$ (ns)
4.7	0	Core	15.38	48.53	36.09	0.14	1.04	7.15	6.1
	3	Core	13.65	44.89	41.47	4.0	22.5	120.8	103.4
		T-II	3.06	22.49	74.44	44.2	314.9	1433.9	1362.7
4.1	0	Core	17.25	48.53	34.22	0.09	0.76	5.32	4.5
	3	Core	20.00	41.69	38.31	3.3	15.7	77.7	65.4
		T-II	4.12	22.22	73.66	45.5	289.4	1497.0	1428.2
3.2	0	Core	16.73	46.41	36.86	0.9	8.4	40.5	33.6
	3	Core	12.86	55.69	31.45	6.0	31.0	126.5	96.4
		T-II	3.58	42.19	54.23	78.9	405.9	1164.2	999.0

Table TS8. Relative PLQY of the core CdSe NRs ($\langle d \rangle = 3.2$ nm) and 1, 5, and 7 ML of ZnO shell deposited on CdSe NRs.

NRs	ML _{cal}	PL _{Core} (nm/eV)	PL _{T-II} (nm/eV)	PLQY (%)
$\langle d \rangle = 3.2$	0	552/2.25	-	1.8
	1	573/2.16	770/1.61	7.34
	5	583/2.13	786/1.58	10.79
	7	588/2.11	800/1.55	12.60

Table TS9. The relative PLQY of core CdSe NRs ($\langle d \rangle = 4.1$ nm) and 1, 5, and 7 ML of ZnO shell deposited on CdSe NRs.

NRs	ML _{cal}	PL _{Core} (nm/eV)	PL _{T-II} (nm/eV)	PLQY (%)
$\langle d \rangle = 4.1$	0	617/2.01	-	0.17
	1	640/1.94	879/1.41	2.46
	5	641/1.93	853/1.45	3.36
	7	635/1.95	861/1.44	2.44

6. Electronic absorption and PL spectra

Figure S8. The optical properties of the CdSe NRs ($d \sim 4.1$ nm) for different shell thicknesses (a) UV-Vis absorption spectra, (b) PL emission spectra.

Figure S9. UV-Vis absorption and PL emission spectra of ZnO NCs.